

Predictive model for energy consumption of electric-vehicle battery

with consideration of self-uncertainty route factors

1. Introduction

Decarbonisation of large urban areas has become imperative for reducing the emissions of greenhouse gases (GHGs) and other air pollutants. Road transport is one of the key factors responsible for the current climate-change situation (OICA, 2019), mainly owing to the extreme dependence on internal combustion engine vehicles (EEA. European Environment Agency, 2018; IEA. International Energy Agency, 2019a). The current situation is considered to be unsustainable, and consequently, the renewal of urban mobility finishing with the dependence on fossil fuels is imperative for achieving global warming mitigation and improving the air quality (EEA. European Environment Agency, 2019). In this context, the main options have mostly been focused on the use of alternative powered vehicles. Among them, battery electric vehicles (BEVs) are considered to be the most promising (Egbue and Long, 2012; Fernández and Giménez, 2019) for the transition to sustainable mobility (Beirigo et al., 2018; Fernández, 2019). However, although the adoption and market share of these vehicles are gradually increasing (IEA. International Energy Agency, 2019b; Lutsey, 2017), it is necessary to overcome existing barriers and foster the popularisation of these less-polluting vehicles. They should be given a more appropriate name than “zero-emission vehicles,” because they do not fully mitigate emissions; they generate pollutants indirectly when recharging batteries from the electric grid (Álvarez Fernández, 2018). Thus, energy saving is the relevant topic, contributing to both direct (tailpipe) and indirect emission abatement.

Urban planning policies have historically been influenced by diverse factors, giving support to ICVs, prioritising the reduction of traffic congestion, and managing pedestrians over tailpipe emissions. Consequently, the most populated cities share the same problem: the randomness of the traffic-control elements and regulations and their effects on the vehicle speed cycles, fuel

consumption, and emissions. Most BEV energy consumption studies have focused on optimal routing evaluation based on different criteria, e.g. the fuel consumption (Chang and Morlok, 2005), time windows (Zuo et al., 2019), cost reduction due to energy saving (Xiao et al., 2019), minimal operating costs, pollutant treatment of micro-grids, load variations (Lu et al., 2018), and State of Charge for battery swap (Zhang et al., 2019). However, the relevance of traffic-control elements and their randomness is usually neglected or is considered as part of the driver behaviour influence on their estimations, considering real-world inputs.

The effect of traffic element control on electric-vehicle (EV) consumption analysis is not a new research topic and has been investigated in several studies. For example, route boundary conditions and vehicle dynamics were considered for energy savings (Vatanparvar et al., 2015), and a vehicle was examined under different traffic conditions (Yao et al., 2013). Nevertheless, for a completely unbiased traffic-regulation assessment, the driver's influence must be neutralised. This was demonstrated in the studies of Sentoff et al. (2015), where the driving style significantly affected the energy figures; Wu et al. (2015), where the selection of the optimal driving speed was based on the road characteristics and real-time traffic conditions; and Qi et al. (2017), where data were obtained by combining OBD and global positioning system (GPS) information. Other studies (Paffumi et al., 2018; Tsiakmakis et al., 2017) focused on the Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicles Test Cycle, which is based on the acquisition of different driving samples, referring to the drivers and city elements. In one study (Kozlak and Wach, 2018; Zambrano-Martinez et al., 2018), databases were created from particular real-world cases, being strongly biased by the human factor and location. All these studies converge on the difficulty of modelling route boundary conditions; the researchers did not determine whether the speed profiles were influenced by traffic-regulation policies, which may have obviated the randomness of the speed profiles and hidden the fact that the true origin of the vehicle driving profile lies in the city traffic regulatory structure.

The first approximation of the problem was recently published (Fernández et al., 2019). The degree of the impact on the energy calculation was demonstrated, and a methodology for calculating the average consumption and the relationship between the uncertainty inherent to

these city elements and the mobility scenarios was developed. The objective of the present study was to expose the significance and influence of the city (related to its inherent uncertainty), providing a method for traffic-regulation management and energy-consumption evaluation. The proposed approach is an extension of a previously published methodology for analysing the city traffic-regulation elements that most significantly affect the BEV energy consumption. These factors must be easily identifiable and modifiable by policymakers who implement new urban policies. Additionally, all the relevant information must be provided, and the boundary conditions for energy-consumption evaluation must be established, regardless of the type of EV. To achieve these goals, a predictive model was developed, where the stochastic route factors were considered and the human-factor bias was neutralised. This methodology was conceived for predicting how the energy requirements for BEVs are affected by changes in mobility management, and it can help urban planners and vehicle fleet managers for last-mile delivery or car-sharing companies, among others. The importance of environmental issues has a tangible impact on supply-chain management (Jabali et al., 2012). For the sustainable production and distribution of products, both environmental and social factors must be considered, as the economic impact of logistics has wider effects of pollution on the environment. Industrial organisations must develop and investigate strategies to adopt greener applications and consider the moderated use of natural resources as their social responsibility. Government and customer demands are making environmental responsibility an increasingly important factor in supply-chain operations.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 focuses on the development of the proposed methodology. In Section 3, the results are presented. Section 4 presents a case study for the city of Madrid, and Section 5 presents a discussion. Finally, conclusions and suggestions for future work are presented in Section 6.

2. Methodology

The main objective of this study was to construct a predictive model for the effect of the randomness of city traffic control on the BEV energy consumption. For this, the city was considered as a set of traffic-regulation stochastic elements that generate different random driving scenarios, affecting the BEV speed profile when a vehicle covers a route within the city boundaries. The stochastic speed profiles were useful for determining these driving scenarios and the corresponding energy consumption. Once the stochastic relationships were determined, the multiple linear regression method was used to visualise and identify the factors with the greatest effect on the vehicle consumption, reducing the computational effort. Thus, assessing the effects of city traffic elements on the energy consumption was an achievable task, and it was possible to identify where efforts should be focused to enhance the electric mobility. **Figure 1** presents a diagram of the methodology workflow, and Subsections 2.1–2.3 explain the steps followed.

Figure 1. Workflow diagram of the methodology.

2.1 Energy-consumption approach

According to a previous approach (Fernández et al., 2019) for calculation of the net energy consumption based on the discretisation of the path in basic standardised evaluable units called stretches, allowing standardisation of the measurement unit of a route. The influence of the driver behaviour is minimised by assessing the objective of defining an unbiased methodology. The driving actions are restricted to two possibilities: a drive-through at a fixed maximum allowed speed along the stretch, and a stop (from the speed limit to zero) and go, followed by reaching the speed limit again, because of a stop-event intervention according to its random nature.

The overall representative result for the speed of consecutive stretches that constitute a route defines a stochastic route speed profile (SRSP). To calculate the energy consumption within a stretch, its length (x) is established according to the distance travelled during the action of stopping from the maximum allowed speed (v), decreasing speed at a fixed acceleration until stopping, waiting for the stop event finish, and then increasing speed at a fixed acceleration until the maximum allowed velocity is reached. Thus, a stretch can contain either of the two actions in driving; otherwise, it would not be possible to establish a neutral stretch length. To establish the stretch length, motion under a constant-acceleration formula is applied. In both cases, the acceleration (a) is defined as a fixed value to neutralise human intervention, and the stretch length depends entirely on the maximum speed allowed. This acceleration is a configurable factor that can assume any representative real-world value. Hence, the stretch length does not vary while its maximum speed remains constant, allowing the standardisation of route stretches and simplifying the interpretation for calculations. As in the case of a complete route, the maximum allowed speed may affect the stretch length. To simplify the mathematics, the sub-route is defined as a set of consecutive stretches that have the same maximum allowed speed. Accordingly, a route is composed of several consecutive sub-routes with a specific speed limit, each containing a certain number of stretches, where it is possible to stop.

According to these assumptions, there were three types of speed behaviour in a stretch according to its nature: O_I represents the stretch type where the speed is constant and no stopping

action occurs, O_2 represents the stretch type where the vehicle stops and starts, and O_3 includes stretches located between two sub-routes, where the vehicle increases or decreases its speed, equalising the speed from one sub-route to the next. The energy consumption of each stretch type can be calculated using vehicular dynamics equations, as in previously published works (Fiori et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017). The present study was constrained within this theoretical framework, because if a real-world vehicle was used, the analysis would have been biased by the driver's behaviour. The energy consumption, CP_{BEV} , of a particular vehicle defined for stretch type O_1 , considering the null road slope, is expressed by equation (1):

$$CP_{BEV}(constant\ speed) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot C_d \cdot A \cdot v^3 t + M \cdot g \cdot v \cdot t \cdot \tau, \quad (1)$$

where ρ represents the air density, C_d is the aerodynamic coefficient, A represents the frontal area, v represents the maximum allowed speed within the sub-route, t represents the time, M represents the vehicle mass, g represents the gravitational acceleration, and τ represents the rolling resistance coefficient. When the BEV stops and goes, it is necessary to evaluate the two corresponding actions: braking (equation (2)) and acceleration (equation (3)). When the vehicle brakes, its speed decreases from the maximum allowed speed to zero ($v_{final} = 0$), and then the vehicle accelerates until it reaches the speed limit again. In this case, $v_{initial} = \text{zero}$, and $v_{final} = v_{sub-route}$). During vehicle braking, it is possible to recover part of the energy, depending on the regenerative braking effectiveness (α) (Lv et al., 2015), which is configurable regardless of the type of BEV but is fixed at the beginning of the methodology.

$$CP_{BEV}(braking) = \int_0^{t_{braking}} P(t) \cdot dt = \int_0^{t_{braking}} F(t) \cdot v(t) \cdot dt = \int_0^{t_{braking}} [-(M \cdot a) + \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot C_d \cdot A \cdot v(t)^2\right) + (M \cdot g \cdot \tau)] \cdot v(t) \cdot dt \quad (2)$$

$$v(t) = v - a \cdot t$$

Here, $v(t)$ represents the instantaneous speed, a represents the constant acceleration, and $t_{braking}$ represents the braking time. α is not included in equation (2), because it can be added at the end of the net-energy calculation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 CP_{BEV}(acceleration) &= \int_0^{t_{acc}} P(t) dt = \int_0^{t_{acc}} F(t) \cdot v(t) \cdot dt = \int_0^{t_{acc}} [M \cdot a + \\
 &\quad \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \rho \cdot C_d \cdot A \cdot v(t)^2 \right) + (M \cdot g \cdot \tau)] \cdot v(t) \cdot dt \quad (3) \\
 v(t) &= a \cdot t
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, $v(t)$ represents the instantaneous speed, a represents the acceleration, and t_{acc} represents the accelerating time.

For transition stretches (O_3), it is only necessary to apply the equation of braking or acceleration, and the different initial and final speeds for this stretch type are the speeds of the sub-routes between which the transition section is located.

The driving actions are conditioned by the uncertainty associated with the stretch, which represents the probability of non-stop (P_i) or stop ($1-P_i$) event occurrence, defined with these probabilities, respectively. Thus, each sequence of driving actions is also defined by its probability of occurrence, which means the number of O_1 and O_2 stretches in each sub-route that composes an entire route. Since the number of stops and no-stops, this implies that the same amount of energy consumption can be obtained with different ordering of the same events; therefore, for the probability calculation, all the possible combinations must be considered.

Figure 2 presents an example of the SRSP actions and the probability sequence.

Figure 2. Example scheme of the SRSP, displaying the subsets, stretch types, and driving actions.

The net energy consumption of all possible sequences of stretches in each sub-route $i = \{1 \dots p\}$ was calculated ($En_{sb,i,j}$) (considering that the BEV recovers energy during braking and considering their probabilities ($P(En_{sb,i,j})$), according to the number of stopping events within $j = \{0 \dots n_{sub}\}$ and their respective probabilities. In the sum of the consumed and recovered energies, α is included, but the probability of each sub-route sequence is only expressed once, because if a stop occurs, the braking and acceleration actions share the same probability. Equation (4) describes this procedure:

$$NC_{sb} = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} En_{sb,i,1} = Ec_{sb,i,1} - \alpha \cdot Er_{sb,i,1} \\ En_{sb,i,2} = Ec_{sb,i,2} - \alpha \cdot Er_{sb,i,2} \\ \vdots \\ En_{sb,i,r} = Ec_{sb,i,r} - \alpha \cdot Er_{sb,i,r} \end{array} \right. \left. \begin{array}{l} P_{sb,i,1} \\ P_{sb,i,2} \\ \vdots \\ P_{sb,i,r} \end{array} \right\}. \quad (4)$$

Thus, the net consumed energy can be considered as a discrete random variable. This random variable describes the net energy consumption NC_{sb} for a sub-route, in accordance with equation (5), as well as the mean ($E(NC_{sb})$) and the variance ($VAR(NC_{sb})$).

$$NC_{sb} = \begin{cases} En_{sb,i,1} & P(NC_{sb} = En_{sb,i,1}) \\ En_{sb,i,2} & P(NC_{sb} = En_{sb,i,2}) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ En_{sb,i,r} & P(NC_{sb} = En_{sb,i,r}) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

To explain the net consumed energy for the entire route, it is defined as a random variable NC_{route} , which represents the sum of all the sub-route discrete random variables that compose the route. The central limit theorem (Alvarado and Batanero, 2006; Ross, 2018) is employed to assign a normal distribution to NC_{route} . Being transition stretches that impose acceleration or braking for connecting two sub-routes, these O_3 stretches cannot be considered as random variables. Thus, the total energy consumption of all the transition stretches was computed. Equation (6) gives the results of the methodology.

$$NC_{route} \rightarrow N \left(\sum_{i=1}^r E(NC_{sbi}) + \sum_{i=1}^{r-1} Et_i, \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^r \text{Var}(NC_{sbi})} \right) \quad (6)$$

As shown, the random variable obtained depends on factors inherent to both the vehicle and the environment (vehicle mass, air density, etc.) and human factors related to urban design and regulations (maximum speed allowed, number of traffic lights, operation time, and route length). Thus, these factors must be defined precisely for analysing their effects using a regression model.

2.2 Definition of influential variables

As previously mentioned, it is necessary to classify the main factors providing information regarding the energy consumption, which allows characterisation of the influence of the route on the energy consumption. As the main objective of the analysis of the city influence was to establish an unbiased evaluation method, the main factors should allow observation of the energy fluctuations due to their variations. These less relevant variables were neglected, as their representations could be obtained from other variables, or they could not be modified, owing to their nature. For this purpose, an initial discretisation based on the objectives and relationships

between variables is beneficial, because it allows for a reduction in the size of the model, where the main factors should be easily identifiable and modifiable, looking forward traffic-regulation models for enhancing the urban mobility. Thus, the parameters related to the vehicle dynamics (M , Cd , A , a) were discarded, because they remain constant once they are defined at the beginning of the methodology and do not provide relevant information regarding route characteristic variations. The acceleration factor was fixed at the beginning of the methodology, with consideration of a safe stop action, neutralising the influence of human behaviour. It was not included as one of the main variables in the predictive model. Hence, the route factors generated the most significant variations in the energy consumption (regardless of **the EV model**). In previous studies, although the main goal was not to analyse the influence of the uncertainty of city traffic elements, the route factors' relevancy and significance were endorsed. For example, in the study of Sachenbacher et al. (2011), the inputs for the optimal route for the EV energy consumption came from route parameters. Preis et al. (2012) presented an energy-consumption methodology based on the route factors and vehicle dynamics, which was applicable to an urban delivery company fleet, considering the battery constraints. These studies indicate that the development of a predictive model based on route parameters is feasible. The factors related to boundary conditions, such as the gravitational acceleration (g), air density (ρ), and rolling resistance coefficient (τ), are not considered, because they remain essentially constant in a city route, thus not satisfying the assessment requirements. The remaining parameters related to the city—which are considered—are the (1) route length, (2) number of stopping elements, (3) probability to stop, (4) maximum allowed speeds, and (5) speed variation. They all satisfy the main conditions for city influence analysis, and they are analysed and modified as input information sources for the energy-prediction model.

Route length

The route length is one of the most relevant variables and the easiest one to acquire because it is defined by the origin and destination of the analysed route. This factor always provides

relevant information for the SRSP methodology. It is—together with the maximum allowed speeds—the basis on which the numbers of stretches, sub-routes, and transition stretches are calculated. Furthermore, it provides boundary limits of the route, locating the route on the map that, depending on neighbourhood, it would be more or less traffic stopping elements. For these reasons, the route length is defined as one of the most influential variables and is identified as L_{route} in the methodology.

Expected number of stop and go events within route

The nature of the different stop events and their respective probabilities present a difficult task. Thus, it is necessary to define a variable that provides information regarding the possible stop actions that can occur within a route owing to the actions of the different traffic-regulation elements. The concept of the stretch only allows one stop. Therefore, it is possible to define a random variable n_x that represents the number of stops in a stretch, which is expressed by equation (7).

$$n_x = \begin{cases} 0 & P_i \\ 1 & (1 - P_i) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Considering this, the expected number of stops that can occur when the vehicle drives along a route is one of the most influential factors. It is related to not only the number of stops but also their respective probabilities. As each stretch is independent, it is possible to confirm that the number of stops in the complete route is a random variable defined as the sum of the random variables n_x that comprise the route. $n_{exp\ route}$ represents the number of stops in the route, and its mean is calculated using equation (8).

$$E(n_{exp\ route}) = \sum_{i=1}^N E(n_x)_i = \sum_{i=1}^N (1 - P_i) = N - \sum_{i=1}^N P_i \quad (8)$$

Here, $E(n_{exp\ route})$ represents the mean of $n_{exp\ route}$, N represents the number of stretches that comprise the route, $E(n_x)_i$ represents the mean of the variable n_x for each stretch, and P_i represents the non-stop probability for each stretch.

Expected average speed for route

A route is composed of several sub-routes, each of which is defined by the maximum allowed speed. In previous studies, researchers assumed a constant speed for route assessment (Artmeier and Haselmayr, 2010; Goeke and Schneider, 2015) and did not consider the variations caused by stop events (Fontana, 2013; Schneider et al., 2014). However, this assumption was not made in the present study, because the variations in the energy consumption due to the maximum-speed changes caused by the traffic-element uncertainty are the basis of the proposed energy-estimation methodology. Consequently, the driving profile cannot be considered as a deterministic value, and it must be assumed as a random variable. Referring to previous works, the average speed provides information regarding all the different speeds of the route (Hill et al., 2013; Nunzio et al., 2017). Accordingly, the average speed of the route, i.e. \bar{v}_{route} , is one of the most influential random variables and is subjected to probabilities. There are three stretch types— O_1 , O_2 , and O_3 —and consequently three different stretch average speeds. In the case of O_1 , the average speed is the maximum allowed speed of the sub-route, because there are no speed variations. In the case of O_2 , the speed is given by a piecewise function, owing to braking and acceleration actions. In the case of O_3 , the speed depends on the maximum allowed speeds of the sub-routes among which it is located (\bar{v}_t). **Figure 3** shows the three stretch speed profiles and their associated average speed values.

Figure 3. Speed profiles for stretch types O_1 , O_2 , and O_3 .

Considering these three possible stretch cases, the discrete random variable of the stretch average speed was defined. $\bar{v}_{stretch}$ represents the average speed for a stretch within a sub-route. Equation (9) defines the random variable $\bar{v}_{stretch}$.

$$\bar{v}_{stretch} = \begin{cases} v_{O_1} & P_i \\ \bar{v}_{O_2} & (1 - P_i) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

In **Figure 3 a)**, the value of \bar{v}_{O_1} is equal to the maximum allowed speed in the sub-route, because there is no stopping action when the vehicle drives at a speed limit constantly through the stretch. As shown in **Figure 3 b)**, for the O_2 stretch type, \bar{v}_{O_2} is the average of a piecewise function v_{O_2} , because a stopping action is required. Thus, as mentioned previously, two different actions occur in the stretch (first part: braking until a total stop; second part: accelerating from zero to the maximum allowed speed). This is expressed by Equation (10).

$$v_{O_2}(x) = \begin{cases} \sqrt{v_0^2 - 2ax} & 0 \leq x \leq x_1 \\ \sqrt{2a(x - x_1)} & x_1 \leq x \leq x_{sub} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Here, v_{O_2} represents the speed for the O_2 stretch, a represents the acceleration, v_0 represents the initial speed (maximum allowed speed for sub-route), x is the distance variable, x_1 represents the distance from zero to the centre of the stretch, and x_{sub} represents the stretch length. By applying the average value for a piecewise function, \bar{v}_{O_2} is determined using equation (11).

$$\bar{v}_{O_2}(x) = \left(\frac{1}{x_2}\right) \cdot \left(\int_0^{x_1} \sqrt{v_0^2 - 2ax} dx + \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{2a(x - x_1)} dx\right) \quad (11)$$

For O_3 stretches, evaluating its \bar{v}_{O_3} only will be considered one of the two actions (braking or accelerating), depending on the speed limits between them. However, in this case, the average speed does not depend on whether the vehicle brakes or accelerates, as long as the speeds in between are the same. This is because the acceleration term is constant. Therefore, the average speed of transition stretches is defined by equation (12).

$$\bar{v}_{O_3}(x) = \left(\frac{1}{x_t}\right) \cdot \left(\int_0^{x_t} \sqrt{v_0^2 - 2ax} dx\right) \quad (12)$$

The next step is to define the average speed of the sub-route, which is also considered as a random variable because the probability related to stop ($1-P_i$) or non-stop (P_i) affects the speed in each stretch comprising the complete sub-route. Therefore, the sub-route average speed is a random variable defined as \bar{v}_{sub} and represents the average speed of each of the sub-routes within a route, which can be determined using the average of the random variables $\bar{v}_{stretch}$ of all the stretches that compose the sub-route. Equation (13) gives the mean of the random variable \bar{v}_{sub} .

$$E(\bar{v}_{sub}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_{sub}} E(\bar{v}_{stretch})_i}{N_{sub}} \quad (13)$$

Here, N_{sub} represents the number of stretches within a sub-route, $E(\bar{v}_{stretch})_i$ represents the mean of each stretch average speed of the sub-route, and $i = \{1, \dots, N_{sub}\}$. This calculation is possible because all the stretches within a sub-route have the same length.

Analogously, the average speed of an entire route is a discrete random variable. However, it cannot be deduced in the same way as the average speed within sub-routes, because the sub-routes and transition stretches have different lengths. In this sense, the average speed of the sub-routes and transition stretches must be balanced according to their effective lengths, with the average speed of a route defined as a weighted average (Skeivalas et al., 2019). \bar{v}_{route} represents the average speed of a complete route, which is calculated as the weighted average of the random variables \bar{v}_{sub} and \bar{v}_t . Equation (14) gives the mean of the average speed within a route.

$$E(\bar{v}_{route}) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^r (E(\bar{v}_{sub}) \cdot L_{sub})_i + \sum_{j=1}^{r-1} (\bar{v}_t \cdot L_t)_j}{L_{route}} \quad (14)$$

Here, r represents the number of sub-routes, $E(\bar{v}_{sub})$ represents the mean of the average speeds of the sub-routes, L_{sub} represents the length of the sub-route, \bar{v}_t represents the mean speed of a transition stretch, L_t represents the length of a transition stretch, $r-1$ represents the number of transition stretches, and $E(\bar{v}_{route})$ represents the mean of the weighted-average speed within a route.

The most relevant variables are defined according to the concept of unbiasedly evaluating the influence of route traffic-control elements by applying an energy-prediction model explained by readily identifiable variables. To support this variable definition, it was compared with the main factors provided by other standard driving cycles, e.g. the applied driving cycle in the World Harmonised Light-Duty Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP) (The European Commission, 2017; United Nations, 2019). The Class 3 vehicle driving cycle was used because it is defined for what were formerly known as pure EVs. The main factors provided were the driving times, stopping times, distance, percentage of time corresponding to stopping actions, maximum speed, average speed (with and without consideration of the stopping times), and minimum and maximum accelerations. It is reasonable to assume that the energy consumption (and pollutant emissions) could be determined using this information.

The Spanish Government developed a tool called CO2TA for the estimation of vehicle fuel consumption and the associated CO₂ emissions (Spanish Ministry of Development Ministry of Agriculture Food and Environment ('Ministerio de Fomento Ministerio de Agricultura Alimentación y Medio Ambiente de España'), 2013). In this tool, the required main inputs include the route length, the discretisation of the route in basic measurement units (stretches), and the average speed. The variables proposed in that study matched some of the main variables used in previous standardised works; therefore, the factor selection and variable development for the linear multiple regression model were accurate. Although a set of three variables was defined, this number of variables can be changed; nonetheless, during linearisation, with this quantity, the target was achieved efficiently and profitably (Zuo et al., 2019).

2.3 Multiple linear regression method

The multiple linear regression method attempts to model the relationship between two or more explanatory variables and a response variable. The problem solution is known as the dependent variable, and the independent explanatory variables are the predictors and residuals

(Mason and Perreault, 1991). The main goal of this method is to obtain an expression for maximising the prediction accuracy (Rawlings et al., 2001) with the minimum number of variables. The base formula for predictive-model development is presented in equation (15), which is established for defining the sequence for a particular case that contributes to database generation. All the cases for the database have the same structure for the entire multiple linear regression procedure.

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_j x_{ij} + \beta_{j+1} x_{ij+1} \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} + \epsilon_i \quad (15)$$

Here, y_i is the dependent variable for a particular case; β_0 represents the mean response when all the variables are equal to zero, which is also called the intercept; β_j represents the change in the results when x_{ij} increases by one unit but the rest of the predictor values (also called estimators) remain constant; and x_{ij} represents the most relevant variables used in the model. ϵ_i is a residual for the particular case; $i = \{1, \dots, q\}$, where q represents the total number of samples for feeding the database, and $j = \{1, \dots, k\}$, where k represents the total number of most relevant variables. All the particular cases can be defined as a matrix, where Y represents the column array of dependent variables, β represents the column array of estimators, X represents the matrix of the most relevant variables, and ϵ represents the row array of residuals (Friedman and Wall, 2005), as given by equation (16).

$$Y = \beta X + \epsilon$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} y_i \\ \vdots \\ y_q \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & x_{ij} & \dots & x_{ik} \\ & \vdots & & \\ 1 & x_{qj} & \dots & x_{qk} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \beta_0 \\ \beta_j \\ \vdots \\ \beta_k \end{pmatrix} + (\epsilon_i \quad \dots \quad \epsilon_q) \quad (16)$$

Furthermore, in the development of a predictive model, the following assumptions are made (Rawlings et al., 2001):

- The variables cannot be repeated.
- The definition of each variable must be justified.
- A minimum sample size of 10 cases is required per variable within the database.

- The dependent variable and the most relevant variables should have a proportional relationship.
- The mean of the residuals is zero and can be assigned to a normal distribution.

Data collection is necessary, and sampling of no less than 10 cases per variable was performed. The collected parameters were those for route identification, i.e. the foregoing most influential variables (L_{route} , $E(n_{exp\ route})$, and $E(\bar{v}_{route})$), and the net energy consumption (NC_{route}) calculated using the previous methodology. With all these data, a database was generated for feeding the multiple linear regression (in accordance with equations (1)–(14)). A larger database yielded a higher accuracy of the predictive model. Equation (17) was used as the basic formula of the model for the BEV energy consumption within a route based on the SRSP.

$$NC_{route\ i} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 L_{route\ i} + \beta_2 E(n_{exp\ route})_i + \beta_3 E(\bar{v}_{route})_i + \epsilon_i \quad (17)$$

Here, $NC_{route\ i}$ represents the net energy consumption within a route; β_0 represents the mean response when all the variables are equal to zero (also called the intercept); β_i represents the estimators; $L_{route\ i}$, $E(n_{exp\ route})_i$, and $E(\bar{v}_{route})_i$ are the variables most significantly affecting the net energy consumption; and ϵ_i represents the residual. According to multiple linear regression theory, the database is performed by subtracting the figures of the most relevant variables for each case. **Table 1** presents the scheme of the database created to feed the regression model. The samples were numbered from 1 to q , where q represents the total number of observed routes.

Route	L_{route} (km)	$E(n_{exp\ route})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Consumed Energy (Wh)
1	$L_{route\ 1}$	$E(n_{exp\ route\ 1})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route\ 1})$	$NC_{route\ 1}$
2	$L_{route\ 2}$	$E(n_{exp\ route\ 2})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route\ 2})$	$NC_{route\ 2}$
3	$L_{route\ 3}$	$E(n_{exp\ route\ 3})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route\ 3})$	$NC_{route\ 3}$
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
q	$L_{route\ q}$	$E(n_{exp\ route\ q})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route\ q})$	$NC_{route\ q}$

Table 1. Database scheme for the energy-prediction model.

The predicted net energy consumption is denoted as NC_{route}^* , and because the residual value is not predictable, it is not included in the predictive equation (William Navidi, 2006). Consequently, the predictive equation is as follows:

$$NC_{route}^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 L_{route} + \beta_2 E(n_{exp route}) + \beta_3 E(\bar{v}_{route}). \quad (18)$$

Once the required information is assembled, several techniques can be used to determine the β values, and one of the most widely known is the least-squares method. This approach determines the estimators with database samples, reducing the sum of the squared deviation of the dependent variable to its least with the found solution. This involves minimising the residual. These calculations are typically performed using software. In this study, Microsoft Excel was used for the analysis, providing the intercept and estimators. The model results were assessed according to their regression statistics and an analysis of variance (ANOVA), which provided information regarding the levels of variability within the regression model and a basis for tests of significance.

c. The main factors considered were the multiple correlation coefficient (r), which indicated how accurately the output could be predicted by applying the linear regression model of a set of variables, and the determination coefficient (R^2), which indicated how effectively the most influential variables described the output. However, the adjusted R^2 , which is commonly used in multiple regressions, is a more reliable value, because it is adjusted according to the number of predictors in the model (Çamdevýren et al., 2005; Mason and Perreault, 1991). After it has been adjusted, if R^2 is large, collinearity may exist, indicating a strong relationship among the multiple linear regression variables, which can cause redundancies or inaccurate results (Santiago et al., 2018). Conceptually, there are two possible extreme situations: perfect collinearity and no collinearity; nevertheless, in real regression models, there is a certain degree of permissible collinearity between the variables (Baird and Bieber, 2016). In this study, the most influential variables were related; thus, collinearity was expected and evaluated by applying the variance inflation factor (VIF) (Salmerón et al., 2018). Commonly, it is considered that for a VIF of >10 , the collinearity is sufficiently large to cause problems (López González, 2012; Lewis-Beck et al., 1998), and the affected variables should be removed from the regression model (Akinwande et

al., 2015). Although James et al. (2013) considered that the limit value is high, in the present study, it was considered that while the VIF was <10 , the collinearity would not interfere with the results. The null hypotheses of the complete model and each working variable were assessed using the *Sig F* and the *Sig t-stat* values. If they were <0.05 , the model and variables were explanatory (Rawlings et al., 2001). Moreover, the degrees of influence of the variables on the model were analysed using standardised coefficients (beta predictors).

3. Results

A methodology was established for developing a model to predict the net energy consumption directly and simply, with consideration of the uncertainty caused by the elements related to the traffic of the route within the city. A set of the most influential variables, which provide relevant information regarding the main factors of the routes, was defined. A simulation was performed, and the behaviour of the model was verified according to real input data. The results presented were based on a Renault Zoe 40 and its vehicle dynamics data (Renault S.A., 2018), where α was configured at 20%. The acceleration was set as 3.9 m/s^2 according to the Directorate General of Traffic of Spain (DGT) (Directorate General of Traffic of Spain (DGT)(Directorate General of Traffic of Spain' 'Dirección General de Tráfico de España'), n.d.), and this value was used for the results and case study sections. Environmental parameters were taken from the city of Madrid (Spain), corresponding to a zero road grade. These figures are configurable. Moreover, a sample comprising 30 different routes in Madrid was generated. The net energy consumption was calculated for each route. **Table 2** presents the vehicle dynamics and boundary conditions, and **Table 3** presents the route characteristics and database parameters.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Vehicle mass (kg)	M	1480
Frontal area (m ²)	A	2.713
Aerodynamic resistance coefficient	C _d	0.34
Energy recovery coefficient (%)	α	20
Rolling resistance coefficient	τ	0.013
Road angle (°)	Φ	0
Air density at 20°C (kg/m ³)	ρ	1.204
Gravity (m/s ²)	g	9.81
Acceleration (m/s ²)	a	3.9

Table 2. Vehicle dynamics and boundary conditions.

Route	Number of stopping events	Probability to stop	Number of sub-routes	L_{route} (km)	$E(n_{exp route})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Consumed Energy (Wh)
1	31	0.4	3	3.81	12.4	39.53	611
2	31	0.6	3	3.81	18.6	38.47	765
3	31	0.8	3	3.81	24.8	37.40	919
4	36	0.4	3	4.11	14.4	39.89	694
5	36	0.6	3	4.11	21.6	38.71	878
6	36	0.8	3	4.11	28.8	37.55	1062
7	42	0.4	9	4.45	16.8	37.57	694
8	42	0.6	9	4.45	25.2	36.77	847
9	42	0.8	9	4.45	33.6	35.96	999
10	60	0.4	2	6.66	24	46.66	1280
11	60	0.6	2	6.66	36	45.22	1632
12	60	0.8	2	6.66	48	43.78	1984
13	48	0.4	4	12.52	19.2	69.52	2124
14	48	0.6	4	12.52	28.8	68.87	2410
15	48	0.8	4	12.52	38.4	68.26	2691
16	59	0.4	2	7.26	23.6	46.98	1317
17	59	0.6	2	7.26	35.4	45.68	1663
18	59	0.8	2	7.26	47.2	44.39	2010
19	24	0.4	1	2.50	9.6	46.87	492
20	24	0.6	1	2.50	14.4	45.32	634
21	24	0.8	1	2.50	19.2	43.74	777
22	23	0.4	3	3.50	9.2	47.20	565
23	23	0.6	3	3.50	13.8	46.15	701
24	23	0.8	3	3.50	18.4	45.11	836
25	25	0.4	1	3.20	10	47.45	559
26	25	0.6	1	3.20	15	46.19	707
27	25	0.8	1	3.20	20	44.89	855
28	21	0.4	1	2.10	8.4	46.65	421
29	21	0.6	1	2.10	12.6	44.97	546
30	21	0.8	1	2.10	16.8	43.30	670

Table 3. Database of route samples.

Thus, the multiple linear regression method was used for obtaining the predictive model, with the β values given by equation (19).

$$NC_{route}^* = -1007.25 + 81.88 \cdot L_{route} + 30.20 \cdot n_{exp route} + 22 \cdot E(\bar{v}_{route}) \quad (19)$$

The results for the regression statistics, the ANOVA, Sig F, and Sig t-stat are presented in **Table 4**. **Table 5** presents a comparison between the calculated and estimated net energy-consumption values, including residuals.

Regression statistics		ANOVA						
		Source of Variation	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of squares	Mean square	F	Sig F	Sig t-stat
Multiple correlation coefficient r	0.9974							
Decision coefficient of regression model (R ²)	0.9948	Regression	3	11016986.77	3672328.92	1651.64	8.91E-30	<i>L_{route}</i> 1.80E-11
Adjusted R ²	0.9941	Residual	26	57809.55	2223.44			<i>E(n_{exp route})</i> 6.01E-19
Observations	30	Total	29	11074796.32				<i>E(v_{route})</i> 6.10E-11

Table 4. Prediction model statistics and ANOVA results.

Route	Consumed Energy (Wh)	Predicted Energy (Wh)	Residual (%)
1	611	551	9.77
2	765	715	6.50
3	919	879	4.35
4	694	644	7.24
5	878	836	4.86
6	1062	1027	3.24
7	694	693	0.22
8	847	929	-9.70
9	999	1165	-16.60
10	1280	1292	-0.90
11	1632	1622	0.60
12	1984	1953	1.58
13	2124	2131	-0.32
14	2410	2406	0.15
15	2691	2683	0.30
16	1317	1336	-1.43
17	1663	1664	-0.03
18	2010	1991	0.91
19	492	521	-5.94
20	634	632	0.36
21	777	742	4.45
22	565	598	-5.84
23	701	714	-1.79
24	836	830	0.70
25	559	603	-7.99
26	707	726	-2.75
27	855	849	0.77
28	421	447	-6.14
29	546	537	1.57
30	670	627	6.42

Table 5. Results for the consumed and predicted energy, with residuals.

The model was statistically significant, and the variables were strongly explanatory, as *Sig F* and *Sig t-stat* were both <0.05 . The obtained value for the adjusted R^2 was 0.994, which was satisfactory. Thus, the degree of collinearity was assessed using the VIF method, and the results are presented in **Table 6**.

Variable	Standardized coefficients (beta)	VIF
L_{route}	0.3974	6.24
$E(n_{exp\ route})$	0.5264	2.54
$E(\bar{v}_{route})$	0.3100	4.25

Table 6. Standardised coefficients and collinearity of the regression model.

As expected, there was a certain degree of collinearity owing to the characteristics of the variables, and certain routing factors were common. The results indicated that L_{route} had the largest VIF, followed by $E(\bar{v}_{route})$. However, considering the foregoing hypotheses, none of the VIFs exceeded the assumed limit value of 10; hence, this level of collinearity was acceptable. $E(n_{exp\ route})$ was the most relevant variable in the model, while L_{route} and $E(\bar{v}_{route})$ exhibited similar beta values. This may be because $E(\bar{v}_{route})$ and L_{route} were closely related through the formulation methodology, in contrast to $E(n_{exp\ route})$. Nevertheless, considering that in most cases a longer route corresponds to more possible stop events and that only a driving action can occur within a stretch, where its quantity depends on the speed, acceleration, and route length; it would allow concluding L_{route} and $E(n_{exp\ route})$. The residuals followed a normal distribution $N(0, 45)$. Even if the level of collinearity was acceptable, for avoiding eventual disturbances, one of the variables was occasionally removed, either to reduce the computational effort or because this variable did not provide a significant contribution (William Navidi, 2006). In this work, it was considered that scenario, obtaining the results presented in **Figure 4**. The consumed energy is shown, along with the prediction based on the three main variables and the prediction for each iteration.

Figure 4. Results of predictive model iterations.

The normal distribution of the residuals for each model must be evaluated to verify the global results.

- Predictive model $(L_{route}, E(n_{exp\ route}), E(\bar{v}_{route}))$: $adjusted\ R^2 = 0.9941$; residual $N(0,45)$
- Predictive model $(L_{route}, E(n_{exp\ route}))$: $adjusted\ R^2 = 0.9701$; Residual $N(0,103)$
- Predictive model $(E(n_{exp\ route}), E(\bar{v}_{route}))$: $adjusted\ R^2 = 0.9672$; Residual $N(0,108)$
- Predictive model $(L_{route}, E(\bar{v}_{route}))$: $adjusted\ R^2 = 0.8773$; Residual $N(0,209)$

The values of adjusted R^2 and the standard deviations of the residuals led to the same conclusion displayed in **Figure 4**; the prediction model with the three main predictive variables exhibited a better adjusted R^2 , indicating a higher accuracy and smaller variance within the energy prediction errors. Hence, each variable was relevant and representative with regard to the energy consumption.

Before performing the case study and referring to the foregoing WLTP and CO2TA, it could be beneficial to evaluate the accuracy of the model, not only in the defined cases of the database but in a standardised and neutral test. Thus, the boundary conditions were adapted to the predictive-model variables, and the results of the two procedures were compared.

Considering the information provided by the WLTP driving cycle for a Class 3 vehicle, the length of the WLTP cycle was taken as the route length and the average speed without stops (i.e. without time when the vehicle remains stopped), but counting the stopping actions. The WLTP establishes nine stops, which led to interpretation of these nine stopping actions in stretches as the expected number of stops within the route (because the probability to stop for each one was 1), and the acceleration value was taken according to the developed predictive model. When it was applied to these boundary conditions, the obtained consumed-energy prediction for the WLTP was approximately 120 Wh/km; the official WLTP provides an energy consumption of 135 Wh/km for this EV (Renault S.A., n.d.). In the case of CO2TA, the report provided an estimation of 230 Wh/km for the mean energy consumption of an EV for the years 2020 and 2021 (Spanish Ministry of Development Ministry of Agriculture Food and Environment ('Ministerio de Fomento Ministerio de Agricultura Alimentación y Medio Ambiente de España'), 2013). The mean of the predictive model database was 220 Wh/km.

Although these values are similar, some conditions must be taken into account. The acceleration range in the WLTP cycle differs from that of the model developed in this study. The α used in the official WLTP is not provided, and its average speed is given by the calculation space divided by time. These points must be considered, because they may cause divergent results in similar scenarios. For CO2TA, the boundary conditions are different. Additionally, the acceleration range is not specified. Furthermore, this tool is typically used in cases where the speeds are >50 km/h, the speeds remain relatively constant, and traffic congestion is considered (resulting in bias due to the human factor). Thus, these comparison results are useful but should be used to draw definitive conclusions. The results are presented and discussed in Sections 4 and 5 respectively.

4. Case study

A case study involving two common scenarios was considered: (1) a working daily itinerary, with the origin at the Chamartin train station parking lot (**Figure 5**; Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. a)) and the destination at a parking lot in the city centre (the return itinerary routes are displayed in **Figure 5** b)) and (2) a student daily itinerary, with the origin at a student home and the destination at the university campus (**Figure 5** c)); the return itinerary is presented in **Figure 5** d). Both scenarios were set in Madrid, Spain.

a) Outward itinerary 1

b) Return itinerary 1

c) Outward itinerary 2

d) Return itinerary 2

Figure 5. Routes of the case study.

For this case study, only traffic lights were considered as stopping events, taking into account the associated uncertainty. However, a probability model for feeding traffic-light uncertainty was not developed, because the objectives of the study were (1) to assess the influence of traffic randomness on the EV energy consumption and (2) to develop a predictive model suitable for any city assessment. This was achieved by simulating different probability values; therefore, $(1-P_i)$

was varied among 0.4, 0.6, and 0.8. The range of probabilities expanded the routes from the 9 initial routes to 27. The characteristics of the routes are presented in **Table 7** and the obtained results are presented in **Table 8**.

Origin - Destination locations	Figure / Itinerary	Route	L_{route} (km)	Number of sub-routes	Number of stopping events	Probability to stop		
Chamartin parking train station - Parking city centre	5 a) Outward itinerary	A	7.2	2	62	0.4		
		B	7.2	2	62	0.6		
		C	7.2	2	62	0.8		
		D	7.6	2	70	0.4		
		E	7.6	2	70	0.6		
		F	7.6	2	70	0.8		
		G	8	4	91	0.4		
		H	8	4	91	0.6		
		I	8	4	91	0.8		
	5 b) Return itinerary	J	6.96	2	50	0.4		
		K	6.96	2	50	0.6		
		L	6.96	2	50	0.8		
		M	7.95	4	59	0.4		
		N	7.95	4	59	0.6		
		O	7.95	4	59	0.8		
		Student's home – University of Antonio de Nebrija	5 c) Outward itinerary	P	4.33	7	43	0.4
				Q	4.33	7	43	0.6
				R	4.33	7	43	0.8
S	6.15			5	65	0.4		
T	6.15			5	65	0.6		
5 d) Return itinerary	U		6.15	5	65	0.8		
	V		4.73	7	53	0.4		
	W		4.73	7	53	0.6		
	X		4.73	7	53	0.8		
	Y		6.89	10	55	0.4		
Z	6.89	10	55	0.6				
ZZ	6.89	10	55	0.8				

Table 7. Characteristics of the case-study routes.

Route	L_{route} (km)	$E(n_{exp\ route})$	$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Consumed Energy (Wh)	Predicted Energy (Wh)	Residual (%)
A	7.2	24.8	46.7	1352	1361	-0.72
B	7.2	37.2	45.3	1684	1705	-1.25
C	7.2	49.6	43.9	2052	2049	0.17
D	7.6	28	46.5	1443	1487	-3.06
E	7.6	42	45.0	1859	1877	-0.97
F	7.6	56	43.5	2274	2266	0.35
G	8	36.4	44.8	1672	1736	-3.78
H	8	54.6	43.1	2183	2247	-2.94
I	8	72.8	41.4	2693	2759	-2.43
J	6.96	20	46.42	1144	1090	4.74
K	6.96	30	45.33	1422	1402	1.43
L	6.96	40	44.24	1700	1714	-0.80
M	7.95	23.60	45.37	1328	1265	4.75
N	7.95	35.40	44.26	1651	1636	0.90
O	7.95	47.20	43.16	1975	2008	-1.68
P	4.33	17.20	35.90	662	659	0.47
Q	4.33	25.80	35.06	817	900	-10.16
R	4.33	34.40	34.22	972	1141	-17.39
S	6.15	26	40.14	1080	1166	-7.95
T	6.15	39	38.88	1377	1531	-11.18
U	6.15	52	37.63	1674	1896	-13.27
V	4.73	21.20	40.78	914	919	-0.63
W	4.73	31.80	39.34	1169	1208	-3.29
X	4.73	42.40	37.90	1425	1496	-4.99
Y	6.89	22	39.29	1006	1088	-8.19
Z	6.89	33	38.50	1225	1403	-14.53
ZZ	6.89	44	37.72	1444	1718	-18.94

Table 8. Case-study results.

The selection of this set of routes was performed with the inclusion of values within and beyond the bounds of the variables presented in **Table 3**. Thus, the accuracy of the results obtained was verified.

5. Discussion

The results of the case study indicated that the previously calculated NC_{route} and regression-predicted NC_{route}^* energy-consumption values were remarkably similar, reinforcing the idea that the defined variables are sufficient to explain the dependent one. This is in accordance with the expectations for developing a predictive model. Although residuals exist, the prediction accuracy increases as soon as the available routes increase the number of database records, reducing the residuals; thus, the values of the estimators are updated. The most important conceptual limitation of the model (common to all regression techniques) is that it can only ascertain relationships and cannot confirm the underlying causal mechanism.

As explained in Section 4, the most influential term on the energy-consumption prediction corresponds to the random variable for the expected number of stops. As indicated by **Table 3**, **Table 7** and **Table 8**, in many cases where this variable increased, the energy consumption increased. In the case study, the 27 routes connected two pairs of locations in the city of Madrid, with different paths. Routes A, J, P, and V were proposed, which exhibited both the smallest expected number of stops per itinerary and the shortest paths. Increasing the probability to stop resulted in a larger expected number of stops, a lower average speed, and greater energy consumption. However, this trend was not universal; for example, route Q exhibited a higher $E(n_{exp\ route})$ than route V; nevertheless, it had greater energy consumption but lower values than route Y. Additionally, route D was better than routes B and C; it was 400 m longer, had a smaller expected number of stops, and was faster than routes B and C. The results confirm that route D is preferable to routes B and C, being better than route A if a change in its management of stop events would convert it into B or C. Thus, the three predictive variables provide valuable information.

When the origin and destination positions were neglected (only the values in **Table 8** were considered), comparing routes (1) A and M and (2) X and ZZ (expected numbers of stops were similar) yielded the following results. (1) The route M value was slightly lower than the route A value, while route M was 750 m longer than route A. (2) Although route ZZ was longer than route

X, the two routes had similar values for the expected number of stops and the average speed. Routes M and X are better options if only the energy-consumption value is considered but not if the consumed energy per kilometre is analysed (Wh/km). There were patterns among the variables and their behaviours, but the limits of validity of all these patterns were not defined. A variation in the probability of stopping caused an increment in the NC^*_{route} during driving along a path, which allowed the evaluation of the suitability of this variation. However, when different routes are compared, the pattern is not perfectly defined by comparing only one set of routes within the same initial configurable parameters (vehicle dynamics, acceleration, and environment). This problem is inherent to the regression model, and it is impossible to predict whether route A will be better than F by simply using the values of the three predictive variables without being afraid of failure.

Nonetheless, the obtained results are useful because of the main vehicle parameters or the selection of the driving constraints. Thus, a variation of one or a set of the configurable parameters of the model can provide new results, allowing the evaluation of the aforementioned energy-consumption patterns related to the three main variables, in addition to the predictive model. Accordingly, three new scenarios were considered: (1) acceleration of 2 m/s^2 and alpha of 20%, (2) acceleration of 2 m/s^2 and alpha of 80%, and (3) acceleration of 3.9 m/s^2 and alpha of 80%. The results are presented in **Table 9**.

Route	L_{route} (km)	$E(n_{exp route})$	$\alpha=20\%, a=2m/s^2$		$\alpha=80\%, a=2m/s^2$		$\alpha=80\%, a=3.9m/s^2$	
			$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Predicted Energy (Wh)	$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Predicted Energy (Wh)	$E(\bar{v}_{route})$ (km/h)	Predicted Energy (Wh)
A	7.2	24.8	43.93	1317	43.93	826	46.7	846
B	7.2	37.2	41.16	1634	41.16	874	45.3	906
C	7.2	49.6	38.39	1951	38.39	921	43.9	965
D	7.6	28	43.56	1435	43.56	880	46.5	904
E	7.6	42	40.59	1797	40.59	936	45.0	972
F	7.6	56	37.62	2159	37.62	991	43.5	1040
G	8	36.4	41.36	1668	41.36	941	44.8	969
H	8	54.6	37.92	2148	37.92	1018	43.1	1060
I	8	72.8	34.48	2628	34.48	1096	41.4	1152
J	6.96	20	44.34	1162	44.34	777	46.42	790
K	6.96	30	42.21	1420	42.21	817	45.33	838
L	6.96	40	40.09	1678	40.09	856	44.24	887
M	7.95	23.60	43.24	1319	43.24	879	45.37	897
N	7.95	35.40	41.09	1632	41.09	930	44.26	956
O	7.95	47.20	38.93	1944	38.93	982	43.16	1016
P	4.33	17.20	34.32	660	34.32	379	35.90	376
Q	4.33	25.80	32.68	887	32.68	415	35.06	419
R	4.33	34.40	31.04	1113	31.04	452	34.22	462
S	6.15	26	37.81	1139	37.81	654	40.14	665
T	6.15	39	35.40	1483	35.40	710	38.88	731
U	6.15	52	33.00	1827	33.00	767	37.63	796
V	4.73	21.20	37.99	894	37.99	492	40.78	503
W	4.73	31.80	35.18	1155	35.18	527	39.34	551
X	4.73	42.40	32.38	1417	32.38	561	37.90	599
Y	6.89	22	37.82	1071	37.82	697	39.29	703
Z	6.89	33	36.33	1374	36.33	752	38.50	762
ZZ	6.89	44	34.84	1677	34.84	807	37.72	821

Table 9. Case-study routes with different configurations.

When the acceleration was modified, the average speed and energy-consumption values did not change significantly. When the alpha parameter was varied from 20% to 80%, the recovered energy quantity increased significantly, but the variations of the energy-consumption pattern remained the same. $E(n_{exp route})$, i.e. the probability of stopping, was the most influential variable, indicating that the uncertainty inherent to city traffic-control elements significantly affects the driving-speed profiles, energy consumption, and GHG emissions.

Our results and assumptions were compared with those of previous studies to evaluate the progress of the predictive model. In the studies of Fiori et al. (2017) and Liu et al. (2017), there was a remarkable difference in the data collection: a GPS in particular locations and boundary-

condition parameters (e.g. the road gradient, traffic flow, or heating system) were used. This biased the results owing to the influence of the driver's behaviour, which was neutralised in the proposed predictive model, allowing us to observe how the city influenced the energy consumption impartially, regardless of the location and traffic-control element scenarios. A similar bias related to the data collection was observed in the study of Qi et al. (2017). While use of vehicle dynamic equations and the concept for evaluating energy-consumption variations caused by the main variables yielded similar results, the main variables did not match. Distinguishing between the databases, the applied regression methods, and the variables, the R^2 value was 0.8911, and the adjusted R^2 of the proposed predictive model was 0.9941. This indicates the importance of defining the regression variables as well as the accuracy of the proposed predictive model.

A remarkable variation for evaluating the relevance of urban mobility policies concerning the energy consumption of vehicles that allows the most important variables to be better defined is presented according to the discretisation of the route with regard to distance and not the time or traffic flow as in (Zambrano-Martinez et al., 2018). Wu et al. (2015) determined the optimal speed for reducing the energy consumption, considering an exact sequence of stops due to traffic elements, and highlighted the relevance of these elements. In contrast, the developed predictive model can be used in the offline mode with no need for real-time data to perform evaluations. The official WLTP test cycle has a standardised theoretical energy-consumption value (135 Wh/km for Renault Zoe 40), and because the prediction model is configurable, it can be employed as a corrective factor. As shown in **Table 8** and **Table 9**, the predictions of the energy consumption for the routes varied significantly; 237, 227, 121, and 126 Wh/km for route B and 197, 189, 104, and 106 Wh/km for route V.

The results indicate usefulness of the proposed method, which provides—according to quantitative results—conclusions regarding traffic-control elements and their influence on the energy consumption, regardless of the vehicle dynamics. In this sense, the proposed approach can supplement other research works.

6. Conclusions and future work

The objective of this study was to develop a methodology for the assessment of the influence of the traffic-control elements on a BEV driving along a route. In a previous study, according to the uncertainty factors, the authors developed a methodology for evaluating the effects of traffic-control element variations, e.g. the maximum speed allowed or the probability of stopping because of a traffic light, on the energy consumption of BEVs. However, while the method worked well, it did not include an approach to define the importance of each influential factor in the final results. Therefore, the focus of the present study was the development of a predictive model for the expected energy consumption and to understand the existence of predominance regarding any of the explicative terms. The theoretical approach applied to real routes not only allowed the applicability of the proposed method to be verified as a first step for other studies but also allowed the city factors with the greatest influence on the EV consumption to be identified. According to the results, the following conclusions are drawn.

- The stochastic speed profiles represent a novel theoretical methodology for evaluating the energy consumption, including the randomness of traffic-control elements.
- A predictive linear regression model for estimating the vehicle consumption under the influence of traffic-control elements was developed and tested. The definition of a predictable set of variables provides valuable route information. Thus, it is possible to observe the results and make decisions that are not biased by the human factor.
- The predictive model considering the effects of city traffic-control elements on the EV energy consumption indicates that the most relevant variable is the number of expected stops ($n_{exp\ route}$).
- The probability of stopping owing to traffic-control elements significantly affects the predictive model. Thus, the traffic-control element randomness substantially influences the driving actions and largely determines the energy consumption of the EV.

Urban planners can use the proposed model to predict variations in vehicle consumption due to traffic-regulation modifications in urban areas. Hence, it is possible to identify the main

characteristics of a route or a city for establishing comparatives and determine which can be useful for enhancing the electric mobility. The model does not establish a roadmap for sustainability mobility but represents a first step towards achieving this goal.

There remains a considerable margin for improvement and further research. The automation of the process (e.g. using neural-network software) would significantly improve its applicability. Nonetheless, the results presented herein may help policymakers decide on traffic-regulation modifications.